

APPRAISALS TO LIGHT: A FRAMEWORK TO STUDY EMOTION IN RETAIL SPACES

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ABSTRACT

Appraisal Theory, developed in the Psychological Sciences, states that emotion is a result of people's appraisals regarding the effect of a situation over their well-being. The theory has been discussed in the current literature in its relation to design, specifically the design and emotion field. Through a literature review of the Theory and the methods of studying lighting and emotion, a methodological framework is discussed to understand the user's appraisals of lighted environment. Thus, the aim of this paper is to present and discuss a framework to understand the effect of lighting in retail stores on consumer's appraisals and, consequently, their emotions, to be used in research and lighting design projects. Retail environment lighting projects that focus on evoking or preventing certain kinds of emotional experiences might be understood and developed in this research tradition in order to understand if the intended experience was achieved or not.

KEYWORDS: *design and emotion; emotional design; appraisal theory; lighting design; research methods. communication, graphic design.*

INTRODUCTION

Space and architecture fill the experiential voids in the users' lives and provide a collective/shared experience for them. The Standardized Mass Produced Economy, and consequently the Built Space have come a long way since the Industrial Revolution. As Klingmann (2007) states, the key focus of architecture has shifted from 'one size fits all' to 'customization-for-all' economy in today's market.

In a world where brands are ubiquitous, and users have an ever-evolving awareness of the brands, it is imperative for the companies to have a strong spatial presence, one that is clearly distinguishable from the established visual identity. The experience that is created through a stronger visual space, where the primary function is to connect with the user, distinguishes one brand from the other and makes it unique from visual identity. The corporate or retail space, an experiential environment, is the most comprehensive expression of brand culture (Bowen, 1998).

The brands are constantly reinventing the new marketplace or the shrine-like quality that retail spaces are being associated with; this shrine-like quality of brands having a direct connection with its users and their emotions. Many factors

including spatial expression, sculptural quality, sounds, merchandize etc. serve as stimuli that affect the emotions and ultimately the behavior of the users. As Baker et al (1992) point out, according to various studies in the field of retail environment, various parameters including ambient conditions, social variables, and design factors have been studied.

Other studies have included the addition of human variable to the retail environment by Turley (2000). Thus, in this paper, the authors discuss the use of a methodological frameworks to develop research and lighting design projects to evoke or prevent intended emotions, based on Psychological literature, specifically Appraisal Theory.

STUDY OF LIGHTING IN RETAIL ENVIRONMENT

The retail environment is a high-stimulus environment and one such dominant variable that is closely related to the ambient conditions is the lighting of the space. 'Literature indicates that lighting can influence emotions, mood and cognition as well as atmosphere and spatial impressions, although at times the collected findings are inconclusive' (Custers, 2010, pp.331-343).

The lighting industry typically designs to achieve a desired effect for an interior space (Davis, 2011). Several studies are available to assess different parameters of lighting, and several other parameters are available to assess the effect of lighting on human emotion. However, as Davis suggests, the depth and wealth of our research and knowledge of the impact of lighting on visual task performance only underscores the dearth of information on the other aspects of human response to lighting.

The lighting literature available that is helpful in understanding portions of the effect of lighting on human emotional response, and subsequently on environmental cognition, is incomplete without the discussion of studies by John Flynn (1973). Flynn recorded changes to subjective human impressions when the lighting stimuli altered in various architectural settings. Flynn linked lighting changes to various impressions such as spaciousness, visual clarity, privacy, pleasantness, relaxation and complexity. These subjective impressions were closely related to modes in Flynn's experiment. Flynn suggested that the continuum of changes between extremes of these attributes – bright/dim; uniform/non-uniform; central/perimeter; and warm/cool – helped the designers in creating the desired lighting environment. For example, a designer could use non-uniform luminance to create related subjective impressions of pleasantness, sociability, interest etc. Such is the example of separating people visually in a crowded space by using lighting when it is hard to do so physically—a technique often used in cocktail lounges, fine restaurants, and reception rooms. Flynn's study is considered seminal to this day and uses a semantic differential scale to understand the brightness, contrast, and color aspects of lighting, as well as the related subjective impressions of pleasantness, public character, spaciousness, and relaxed nature.

Other studies investigating the effect of spatial and lighting conditions on human psychology have been smaller scale studies directly related to a certain architectural market sector. Fostervold's (2008) study of proportion of direct and indirect lighting on the cognitive performance of office workers tackles the topic of glare and discusses its relation to stress levels at work. The variables assessed were subjective symptoms, subjective well being, and cognitive performance, which enabled data to be gathered on the effect of four ceiling-mounted lighting schemes, which provide different combinations of well-being and cognitive performance related to direct and indirect lighting in ordinary office environments. Boyce's (2003) study of office environments discussed in detail the effects of luminance distribution, non-task surface luminance, and control over lighting on various behavioral outcomes. In Boyce's study lighting professionals prepared questionnaires and observed users under the lighted environment.

Custers et al's (2010) study of lighting in retail environments studies fashion retail shops, and using descriptive appraisal mechanisms concludes that lighting has a potential contribution to perceived ambiance but is only one of numerous elements that may play a role. Three categories of variables – shop interiors, lighting attributes, and perceived atmosphere were assessed and quantified independently by different raters.

Other approaches to studying subjective impressions of a space have included the paired comparisons and semantic differential scaling as employed by Houser (2003) and his team to assess subjective responses to linear fluorescent direct/indirect lighting systems. In a commentary about the said method, Newsham (2003) from the Institute for Research in Construction, Canada, expresses his concern about the several underlying concepts that emerge from semantic differential analysis.

Veitch and Newsham's (2008) study of task performance and the effect of lighting on physiology studies the parameters of brightness, visual attraction, and complexity at a larger scale. The study uses the theory of Linked Mechanisms by David Wyon to tie the different parameters of lighting together. Basically, the approach that employs regression analysis develops a set of links between the lighting features and the routes to worker performance, health, and organizational productivity. Wyon (1996) describes linked mechanisms as elements in built environments that have an effect on behavioral outcomes. For instance, luminance distribution, non-task surface luminance, control over lighting, and other similar variables are 'linked' to the users' behavioral outcomes. Regression analysis that examines whether the influence of one variable (X) on another (Y) is partly or wholly explained by the influence of X on a third variable (M), and the influence of M on Y is the statistical method used in this study.

In the field of subjective impressions in retail lighting, a recent study by Schielke (2010) investigates the effect of lighting in corporate communication. For this study, computer visualizations of retail outlets with different lighting variations were evaluated in terms of light, spatial setting, and brand impression using the semantic differential technique, a method of quantifying a stimulus and subjective reactions on a scale.

In the above-mentioned literature, synthesized in Table 1, the study of lighting has been isolated to a market typology i.e. office, retail, commercial, and it has been limited within the parameters that have been studied.

As the reader can see in Table 1, distinct lighting attributes are evaluated in different lighting studies. As most lighting practitioners and researchers would agree, ignoring any one of the facets of lighting design would not constitute an accurate study of the subject. John Flynn's approach to lighting design is still the benchmark of understanding subjective impressions as it tackles the issues of brightness, contrast, and color – the three closely related qualities of light. Another quality of light that may easily change from sparkle to glare depending on observer's subjective impression, thereby causing a physiological and psychological reaction, should be studied. However, the understanding of subjective impressions is another study that cannot be undertaken in isolation without studying the inherent affect, emotions, and the appraisals of these emotions. For this reason the study must consider brightness, contrast, color and directionality (glare) in the development of a framework in order to understand the relations between light and emotion.

Study	Space attributes		Lighting attributes			
	Related Space	Visual Attraction of Space	Brightness	Contrast	Color	Directionality (Glare/ Sparkle)
Flynn	General		X	X	X	
Boyce	Office					X
Custers	Retail	X	X			X
Houser	Office		X	X		
Veitch/Newsham	Office		X			X
Schielke	Retail	X			X	
Proposed Framework	General		X	X	X	X

Table 1: Synthesis of lighting attributes studied in the current literature and the proposed framework. Source: The Authors

When referring to emotions, we usually mean all the affective phenomena that help us to understand and deal with life, connecting us to or pushing us away from people, things, events and actions (Frijda, 1986). Some examples are love, hate, desire, disgust, and fear.

In the following section we focus on Appraisal Theory, one of the most widely adopted theories of emotion, and also the basis for the discussed framework.

APPLYING APPRAISAL THEORY TO DESIGNING WITH LIGHT

In the cognitive tradition of emotion research, appraisals are understood as the cause of emotions. Appraisal Theory states that appraisals are evaluations from people regarding the effect of an event or situation (including retail spaces) over their well-being, as potentially beneficial or harmful (Arnold, 1960). In the appraisal tradition, it is understood that the way someone processes the information regarding an event causes and determines the emotion, rather than the event itself (Lazarus, 1991).

In terms of lighting, a wash of diffuse light in a retail space creates a more uniform light, and thus has the potential to make you feel comfortable and assist you in making your selection of merchandise. An expected emotional response could be your evaluation about the space making you feel softened and relaxed. On the other hand, a high-contrast environment with pockets of bright and dark areas, and display areas marked with sparkle and focal glow in a huge space crowded with stimuli (clothes, e.g.), could make you feel confused and cause difficulty in concentrating and focusing on what you are looking for, causing irritation or disappointment. Both examples are based on the authors' professional experience. Thus, these responses are likely to change if for various consumer types who experience similar situations. For example, consumers that enjoy the drama that lighting creates may feel bored and disinterested in a uniform environment.

These examples go against the mainstream idea in lighting studies that the events and places themselves are more meaningful than what people capture from and see in them. Every market segment, or consumption group, with their cultural and psychological characteristics, tend to understand the environment in a different way.

If a professional wishes to develop a lighting project that causes a specific and intended effect at the emotional level, they must pay attention to how the target responds to a variety of stimuli and to what generally causes, to these specific kinds of people, the intended experience. Appraisals mediate products and emotions, and ultimately reasons why different people experience different emotions when appraising the same product (Scherer, 1984; Hekkert and Desmet, 2007).

Appraisal Theory has been explored in its relation to design (Demir, Desmet and Hekkert, 2009). "Emotional Design" is a design field concerned with either evoking or preventing certain emotions. Lighting projects focusing on causing or avoiding certain kinds of emotional experiences might be understood and developed in this research tradition.

In psychology, this research tradition based on the analysis of appraisals has at least two clear different approaches, defined as thematic and componential, named in Smith and Lazarus (1990) as "molar" and "molecular".

The thematic approach treats appraisals as summary statements reflecting the general meaning of a situation to a person. It is defined as an appraisal theme. Lazarus (1991) states that each discrete emotion, e.g. sadness or joy, is connected to a different overall meaning, e.g. irrevocable loss or progress towards realization of a goal, respectively.

The componential approach does not understand appraisals as unidirectional. It describes them as a result from distinct questions, each one focusing on a different aspect of the situation (Roseman, 2001; Scherer, 2001). The people's response to each one of these questions composes the appraisal components. They are described and discussed in their relation to lighting issues, as follows.

Motive Consistency

How does the space and the lighting of an environment relate to the consumer's motives to visit a particular store? This would be the main question related to motive consistency, and it is related not just to the functional characteristics of a retail space, but also to its effect over the person's needs, concerns, or goals, regarding self-expression or social symbolism. Positive answers tend to be connected to positive emotions. For instance, when a consumer first arrives at a luxury retail store and sees focal glow created by focused lights on a mannequin wearing a cocktail dress, the consumer in our example is looking for self-gratification and luxury. In this process, the consumer might feel joy and satisfaction while admiring the dress and ultimately purchasing it. We can say that the appraisal is the consumer's thought that the product is exclusive and luxurious, and it relates to the consistency of the purchase motive (self-gratification). The emotional effects are joy and satisfaction.

Research on this target might be used in design briefs. In order to create joy and satisfaction to jewelry consumers looking for self-gratification and luxurious experiences, the lighting designer may use different lighting techniques such as the one described above on the most exquisite and exclusive pieces.¹

Intrinsic Pleasantness

To what extent is the lighted environment pleasant to the consumer? Intrinsic pleasantness is about the sensorial dimension and its adaptation to the situation. Pleasantness is usually connected to emotions like desire (positive), whilst unpleasantness is often related to emotions like disgust (negative). As an example, a playful color-changing LED display behind the showcase window for a teddy bear may make a child interested even more in a toy, causing fascination or admiration (emotional response), due to the thought that it is funnier and more dynamic than the others (appraisal). On the other hand, an excessively bright light above a restaurant table can be the cause of irritation and alarm (emotional response), due to disability glare and subsequently may create the thought in the customer's mind that the space is poorly planned (appraisal).

Considering the first example, a design brief can identify colorful and intermittent lights as the keys to designing a display that causes emotions like fascination or admiration among kids. These would be the parameters that a lighting designer would use to manipulate lighting to achieve an intended emotional response in a retail environment.

Expectation Confirmation

To what extent does the space and the lighting of the environment meet the consumer's expectation? The appraisal is a confirmation or a violation of a person's expectations, which ranges from unexplored aspects of the space to the conse-

1. It is important to highlight that all examples are fictional and refer to the authors' experiences and retail design projects.

quence of an action by the person when in the place. For example, an excessively illuminated pub in diffused fluorescent lamps may create an environment similar to an office—an effect that may lead people to think they are not allowed to relax when drinking alcoholic beverages (appraisal). The resulting emotions can be contempt towards the place, as well as alarm regarding their own behavior, and ultimately result in an environment that is not conducive to social interaction.

In order to avoid people being alarmed and too conscious about their own behavior, and also the contempt regarding a pub that does not provide the relaxing atmosphere they want, a lighting design brief should emphasize diffuse and low lighting.

Standards Conformance

How does the space and the lighting of the environment relate to standards the consumer is used to? The response can be a confirmation or a violation. Every different condition will be processed and understood differently by distinct types of consumers. For instance, when a consumer goes to a low-end store to buy a new pair of shoes, if the lighting of the display is high-contrast, rich, and creates an ambience of luxury, the consumer may mistake the store to be high-end and the said product to be out of his buying power (appraisal), thus resulting in emotions such as embarrassment and contempt.

The reader might be thinking at the moment that this example could be related to other appraisal components, like intrinsic pleasantness, and of course it is. We are highlighting it as an example of standards conformance both to show that the same element can be related to more than one appraisal component, and that the standards that people are used to dealing with also tend to interfere in their evaluation. In the mentioned example, the resulting emotion shows that overcoming expectations is not always desirable and this fact should be considered in design briefs.

Certainty Component

How certain is the user about the timeless quality of the stimuli for the future? Uncertainty is usually connected to fear and hope, and certainty to happiness and sadness.

The immaterial characteristic of light makes this appraisal component indicative of a peripheral interest in lighting studies and design briefs. Since the lighting stimulation is usually limited in time to consumers, from the studied appraisal components, this is the one that has shown the weekly potential to help understanding user's appraisals and emotions to lighted environments. It is important to highlight, at this point, that this is expected and easily understood, since the appraisal components discussed here are based on experience with products (Demir, Desmet and Hekkert, 2009).

Agency

Who or what is a responsible agency for a given situation, according to the user's opinion? It can be the person, or a

parameter of the space such as lighting, or it could also be the situation. This is the usual question employed to represent the agency component. In lighting studies, it is natural to think that the most common answer will make reference to the environment/situation. The agency component of appraisals therefore, would be the lighting itself. For example, an office lighted with a task lamp over the table and no peripheral lighting may give people a headache when they look up from their visual display terminals. The designer, on the other hand, when reading results from a study with this kind of result, should be critical enough to understand that it is a design problem, not a user problem. In the previous example, the addition of peripheral lighting will not only solve the problem of strained eyes, but will also create the subjective impression of a larger room. The resulting emotion from the given situation tends to be different, facing the two mentioned conditions. It could be anger (not a self-directed emotion), realizing that the space was poorly planned, or frustration (self-directed emotion), by thinking that the resulting lack of concentration it is their fault..

Although on a psychological level it might be interesting to understand these changes, at a design level it may sound uninteresting. All user problems are design issues and project challenges. That is the reason why we consider “agency” another appraisal component of interest in lighting studies.

Coping Potential

Can one understand and mitigate the harmful effect of lighting in the particular space, if that is the case? It is about the user’s (perceived) ability to deal with the undesired adverse aspects of a situation. The intent of the lighting of the space should be to give a perceived control on the environment to the users. A lack in coping abilities can result in emotions like anger or dissatisfaction, whilst a trust in their own ability can lead people to feel confident and satisfied. We would like to ratify that every point-of-view is a world of its own, and that every kind of consumer/person will tend to appraise life situations in distinct ways, leading to different emotional responses to the same events:

If the same situation causes different emotional responses it follows that this situation was appraised differently. Thus, the necessity hypothesis does not allow for factors other than appraisals to determine different emotional reactions toward the same situation (Siemer, Mauss and Gross, 2007, p.593).

This dynamic relation between reality, appraisals and emotion makes us think that the relation between people and design is multidimensional. Although both approaches – thematic and componential – can be useful in emotion research, the thematic approach might be too general to be applied to lighting studies, since themes such as “the progress towards the realization of a goal”, will make it difficult to describe lighting design briefs, due to the lack of specificity. Since the componential approach is multifaceted, although less holistic than describing human experience, we believe it is more adequate to elaborate both lighting design briefs and research on the topic.

RESEARCH ON APPRAISALS: METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

After having discussed the literature behind lighting in retail environments and appraisal theory, this paper now discusses a general framework to be applied to lighting studies, or, more specifically, what is defined here as appraisals to light studies. In a two-part approach, this paper first discusses the kind of theoretical approach that is more suitable to these studies – thematic or componential. And then in the second part, a methodological approach focusing on research methods is discussed.

The “appraisals to light” approach: Theoretical basis

The discussion made on Appraisal Theory suggests that the componential approach might be more suitable to lighting studies, since it provides more useful information on how to develop lighting design projects focused on user’s emotions. The approach understands appraisals as multidirectional, describing them as a result from distinct questions (Roseman, 2001; Scherer, 2001); hence the reason why it seems more suitable to lighting studies. Two fictional examples, focusing on the same appraisal component and on the same retail space, are given to make the point clearer. Applying the same situation to a fashion retail store, one with a lighting design that aims at creating a subjective impression of a luxury store, the following two situations help us understand the approach better.

- Situation A: A male shopper in the said retail environment is looking for a new suit. His motives are related to self-gratification and social expression, and the environment is appraised as luxurious, exclusive and worth visiting. The emotional outcome is arousal and pleasantness.
- Situation B: Another male shopper in the same retail environment is in the store for a new suit as well. However, his motive is more utilitarian, and his idea of luxury is more connected to the quality of the product rather than the experience itself. The environment is appraised as selfish and futile. The emotional outcomes are arousal and unpleasantness.

None of these men have the ‘right’ perception about the lighting, and they can represent distinct consumer groups. It is not for the end user to have the ‘right’ perception about the lighting or the subjective impression that it creates. The retailer should set the target and know which are the right lighting attributes to reinforce the perception of luxury for that particular target group. Emotion psychology brings the idea that different kinds of people can have completely different perceptions and emotions when facing the same scenarios (Arnold, 1960; Lazarus, 1991; Scherer, 1984). This is the case in the above examples.

Following the componential approach, as mentioned above (please, note that the example given is only about one of the seven appraisal components), during an interview in a re-

search project the researcher needs to understand the consumer's motives when attending the store and how particular lighting characteristics relate to them. The information from the research seems to have a greater potential to be applied in lighting design projects, since it gives more specific content to the designer, making it easier to work on the project.

On the other hand, by following the simpler path, the thematic approach, the researcher would, in the data collection, investigate how consumers feel in that environment. The answers could be vague, for example, "it looks nice"; "it is luxurious, I like it"; "it is welcoming". The question is: Would this information be useful? Probably not. This is the reason why the componential approach seems to offer more than the thematic approach to lighting design projects.

The "appraisals to light" approach: Methodological approach

From a design perspective, lighting projects should start by defining the brand attributes to be reinforced among people in retail stores. "Architecture is supposed to shape 'corporate identity', which is also expressed in company logos, websites and merchandise. Nothing is excluded from this policy. As suggested by Koojiman & Sierksma (2007), each brand must have its own easily identifiable architecture with distinctive colours, materials and profile". As the authors explore the relation between brand and retail architecture in their paper, they discuss how they instill the brand further into the consumer through the space and other supporting literature, in discussions by Pine and Gilmore (1999) and Koolhaas (1977).

As Brandston (2008) comments, "light, like music, fills, reveals and creates space." In order to tie the impressions, a brand wishes to create in the user's mind using the space, the space needs to be defined according to the brand and as a parameter, and lighting should define the space.

The designer should then define the subjective impressions that they wish to be created among the shoppers through the lighting. Assuming that as the most common practice, the appraisals to light approach follows the same path, and the second stage would be to investigate, among the target audience, which kind of lighting condition is more likely to evoke or prevent the intended emotions; one that is most beneficial for the brand and is true to the brand's identity.

To understand how an emotional phenomenon can be evoked, qualitative/exploratory research seems to be the best choice, since it focuses on understanding certain stimuli in depth, rather than mapping them objectively (Malhotra & Peterson, 2001). Thus, semi-structured interviews and focus groups, in which photos and videos of retail stores are used, might be the best choices to understand how a specific target group reacts to each kind of lighting scenario, and will increase understanding of how to recreate those reactions in real life. Participatory observation in real market situations can also be useful, even though this method is more demanding and less environmentally controlled by the researcher as it is hard

to identify the participants' ethnicity and gender quantitatively and this may affect the study.

In this process (for in-depth interviews or focus groups), an appraisal interview guide would help the researcher to conduct the data collection. The questions would be based on images of distinct lighting scenarios chosen to understand how to trigger the intended emotions. The questions would be focused on each one of the investigated lighting scenarios (pictures and videos during interviews), and would be elaborated to cover the appraisal components. Questions about motive consistency for a brand that intends to evoke the emotion 'inspiration', could be:

1. What are your motivations when you are looking for products of this specific brand?
2. Look at a picture of a lighted space. How does this environment help (or not) you find what you are looking for in the store?
3. How does this lighting relate (negatively or positively) to what you want?
4. What comes to your mind when you look at the picture?
5. How do you feel about it?

If the answers to questions 1-5 are not connected to the intended emotion – inspiration in this case – the interviewer should ask: Does it look inspiring to you? Why? How should it be to look inspiring? Which one(s) of the other pictures/videos that you have seen would you say is the most inspiring?

By analyzing the content of answers for the seven appraisal components, the researcher/ lighting designer would have a broad range of information to design to evoke the emotion inspiration, leading to the third and last stage: experimentation.

Experiments on design usually manipulate certain variables (independent variables), in order to check their effect over other ones (dependent variables) in a quantitative way, by using structured questionnaires (Christensen, 1989). Common independent variables, in lighting studies, will be brightness, contrast, color and directionality (glare or sparkle). The dependent variable(s) will be the intended brand's emotional associations (in the mentioned example, inspiration).

From the second stage, the researcher/lighting designer can build lighting scenarios (either using digital image, 3D, or real retail stores), and develop experiments to test which of these conceptual scenarios is more adequate to evoke the brand's intended emotions.

In order to evaluate the dependent variables (consumer response), measurement scales must be used that expose the causality relation between dependent and independent variables. Some of the most common in this context will be five-to nine-point agreement scales (towards affirmative and negative sentences elaborated about the evaluated scenarios), and semantic differential scales (which consist in positioning a characteristic/word, e.g. 'love', at the left side of the paper, and, at the right side, its antonym, e.g. 'hate', and the respon-

dents are then encouraged to position their opinion between the words).²

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CONCLUSION

The main goal of the study is to introduce and discuss a methodology for appraisal of lighting in a retail environment. A literature review of existing studies on the subjective analysis of lighting revealed the need for a holistic framework for studying the appraisal of lighting, one that captures the four key dimensions of lighting – brightness, color, contrast, and directionality. Space and its effect on branding is a discussion that is incomplete without the understanding of the subjective impressions it has on the users of the space. The analysis of literature revealed the need for a focus area of study of subjective impression covering various parameters of lighting applicable to various architectural spatial settings.

Appraisal Theory allows emotional design applied to lighting to evoke or restrict a certain emotion. The lighting design of a space and its parameters—brightness, color, contrast, and directionality—may be studied according to various appraisal components. This project's next steps will be to develop empirical studies based on this framework: defining brand attributes and intended emotions to be evoked in retail spaces (step 1), investigating how to trigger them in qualitative research (step 2), and experimenting with designed insights to evaluate the real potential of the designed lighting projects to evoke particular emotions (step 3).

It is crucial to highlight that the third step – experimentation – is a 'must do' stage in lighting studies, since it is the only procedure that will verify if user reactions are what we intend them to be. Other than that, it is common in the psychological literature that people find it difficult to report the actual causes of emotions, and the qualitative research proposes this type of investigation.

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2. Measurements and scales are not the focus of this paper, but the authors suggest that for those less acquainted with measurement scales read Christensen (1989).

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